

**Rapoport's rule explains the range size distribution of butterflies along the Eastern
Himalayan elevation gradient**

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TABLE S2

Table S2.1: Output of the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression between elevational range size of overall species and different groups of butterflies of the Rangeet Valley, Sikkim, eastern Himalaya obtained using Steven's method

Sub-groups	Coefficient	Std.Error	t value	R-Squared	Pr(> t)	FDR adjusted p-value
Overall	0.139	0.034	3.807	0.546	0.002**	0.005**
Nymphalidae	0.081	0.049	1.649	0.162	0.121	0.145
Lycaenidae	0.374	0.078	4.767	0.618	0.001***	0.004**
Pieridae	0.353	0.131	2.688	0.340	0.017*	0.029*
Hesperiidae	0.151	0.129	1.166	0.131	0.273	0.273
Papilionidae	0.312	0.067	4.663	0.707	0.001 ***	0.003**
Palaearctic	-0.157	0.073	-2.149	0.248	0.0510	0.680
Global	0.656	0.043	15.258	0.942	4.06e-10 ***	4.87e ⁻⁰⁹ ***
Oriental	0.126	0.057	2.187	0.254	0.046*	0.069
Monophagous	-0.101	0.062	-1.626	0.158	0.123	0.145
Oligophagous	0.476	0.0514	3.72	0.476	0.003**	0.006**
Polyphagous	0.634	0.0629	10.08	0.879	8.43e-08 ***	5.06e ⁻⁰⁷ ***

Table S2.2: Output of the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression between elevational range size of overall species and different groups of butterflies of the Rangeet Valley, Sikkim, eastern Himalaya obtained using Rohde's mid-point method

Sub-groups	Coefficient	Std.Error	t value	R-Squared	Pr(> t)	FDR adjusted p-value
Overall	0.042	0.150	0.282	0.006	0.782	0.939
Nymphalidae	0.045	0.156	0.293	0.006	0.121	0.484
Lycaenidae	0.130	0.2367	0.293	0.029	0.592	0.938
Pieridae	0.473	0.268	1.760	0.279	0.116	0.484
Global	0.933	0.4661	2.002	0.364	0.085	0.484
Papilionidae	0.178	0.411	0.434	0.026	0.677	0.938
Hesperiidae	-0.011	0.228	-0.048	0.001	0.963	0.939
Palaearctic	-0.155	0.400	-0.389	0.029	0.714	0.938
Oriental	-0.024	0.134	-0.179	0.002	0.860	0.963
Monophagous	0.07046	0.220	0.319	0.008	0.755	0.938
Oligophagous	-0.072	0.115	-0.631	0.0321	0.539	0.938
Polyphagous	0.108	0.252	0.429	0.020	0.678	0.938

Table S2.3: Output of the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression between elevational range size of overall species and different groups of butterflies of the Rangeet Valley, Sikkim, eastern Himalaya obtained using Pagel's method

Sub-groups	Coefficient	Std.Error	t value	R-Squared	Pr(> t)	FDR adjusted p-value
Overall	0.318	0.099	3.205	0.423	0.006 **	0.018*
Nymphalidae	0.192	0.118	1.615	0.157	0.129	0.154
Lycaenidae	0.447	0.167	2.117	0.338	0.018 *	0.253
Pieridae	0.560	0.167	3.357	0.530	0.007 **	0.016*
Hesperiidae	0.531	0.186	2.844	0.473	0.019 *	0.253
Papilionidae	0.709	0.122	5.802	0.827	0.001 ***	0.004**
Palaearctic	0.091	0.248	0.370	0.370	0.723	0.723
Global	0.914	0.076	1.960	0.934	3.01e-07 ***	3.61e ⁻⁰⁶ ***
Oriental	0.344	0.122	2.810	0.377	0.014 *	0.024
Monophagous	0.180	0.124	1.453	0.139	0.170	0.185
Oligophagous	0.334	0.107	3.124	0.428	0.008 **	0.016*
Polyphagous	0.787	0.119	6.607	0.784	2.51e-05 ***	1.51e ⁻⁰⁴ ***

Table S2.4: Output of the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression between elevational range size of overall species and different groups of butterflies of the Rangeet Valley, Sikkim, eastern Himalaya using obtained using cross-species method

Sub-groups	Coefficient	Std.Error	t value	R-Squared	Pr(> t)	FDR adjusted p-value
Overall	0.204	0.062	3.271	0.040	0.001 ***	0.006**
Nymphalidae	0.065	0.090	0.090	0.004	0.471	0.517
Lycaenidae	0.360	0.172	2.086	0.098	0.043 *	0.064*
Pieridae	0.250	0.193	2.948	0.250	0.006 **	0.018*
Global	0.859	0.299	2.867	0.291	0.009 **	0.021*
Papilionidae	0.235	0.255	2.599	0.235	0.016 *	0.027*
Hesperiidae	0.177	0.155	1.142	0.032	0.260	0.336
Palaearctic	-0.197	0.291	-0.677	0.054	0.517	0.517
Oriental	0.163	0.066	2.441	0.027	0.015 *	0.027*
Monophagous	0.121	0.123	0.980	0.018	0.331	0.397
Oligophagous	0.224	0.073	3.065	0.045	0.002 **	0.008**
Polyphagous	0.500	0.142	3.523	0.132	0.001***	0.006**

Table S3: The ordinary least squares (OLS) models for climatic variables and elevational range size of overall species and different groups of butterflies. Model coefficient (Coef), standard error (SE) and R squared values (R²) are presented. Significant associations are marked as * (* = FDR adjusted p < 0.05; ** = FDR adjusted p < 0.01; *** = FDR adjusted p < 0.001). TS- Temperature seasonality, MATR- mean annual temperature range, PS- precipitation seasonality.

Sub-Groups	TS					MATR					PS				
	Coef	SE	R ²	p	FDR adjusted p-value	Coef	SE	R ²	p	FDR adjusted p-value	Coef	SE	R ²	p	FDR adjusted p-value
Global	1956.3	217.500	0.852	0.001**	0.001**	914.3**	136.400	0.762	0.001**	0.001**	-0.505	0.769	0.029	0.522	0.694
Hesperiidae	565.400	652.400	0.077	0.409	0.409	77.140	449.370	0.003	0.867	0.867	-0.029	0.327	0.001	0.930	0.930
Lycaenidae	1092.2	271.900	0.535	0.001*	0.005*	142.5	142.500	0.477	0.003*	0.010*	-0.780	0.510	0.143	0.148	0.600
Monophagous	-453.6	176.200	0.321	0.022*	0.033*	-272.43**	76.640	0.474	0.003*	0.010*	-0.158	0.292	0.020	0.595	0.694
Nymphalidae	178.900	162.600	0.080	0.290	0.316	49.400	82.720	0.024	0.560	0.611	-0.338	0.215	0.150	0.138	0.600
Oligophagous	495.4	179.200	0.353	0.015*	0.026*	215.89*	93.790	0.274	0.037*	0.050	-0.209	0.302	0.033	0.500	0.694
Oriental	350.500	187.700	0.199	0.083	0.111	128.590	97.810	0.109	0.210	0.272	-0.330	0.275	0.093	0.250	0.600
Overall	356.7*	126.600	0.361	0.014*	0.026*	150.06*	67.270	0.266	0.043*	0.050*	49.400	82.720	0.024	0.161	0.600

Palaearctic	- 647.7**	201.5 00	0.42 4	0.006	0.019* *	- 323.57 **	98.77 0	0.43 3	0.006* *	0.013* *	- 0.186	0.363	0.01 8	0.61 6	0.694
Papilionida e	1318.80 0	413.7 00	0.53 0	0.011	0.026* *	47.640	36.72 0	0.15 7	0.227	0.272	- 0.140	0.287	0.02 5	0.63 6	0.694
Pieridae	270.000	239.8 00	0.08 3	0.279	0.316	727.30 0	468.0 00	0.14 7	0.142	0.213	- 0.505	0.685	0.03 7	0.47 4	0.694
Polyphagou s	1987.6* **	198.6 00	0.87 7	0.001* **	0.001* **	944.2* **	121.9 00	0.81 0	0.001* *	0.001* *	- 0.980	0.737	0.11 2	0.20 5	0.600